

Kinetics of Oxidation of 2, Methyl 2, 4-Pentane Diol by Peroxydisulphate Catalysed by Silver(I)

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Received May 14, 1970.

The kinetics of the reaction between peroxydisulphate and 2, methyl 2,4-Pentane diol catalysed by silver(I) have been studied. The rate of peroxydisulphate disappearance was found to be proportional to the concentration of peroxydisulphate and of silver(I), but independent of the concentration of diol. The rate of silver(I) catalysed decomposition of peroxydisulphate in presence of diol is about six times faster than the rate in absence of the diol. The reaction was studied at different temperatures. The specific rate constant k , ΔE , A and ΔS^* have been calculated as 0.2331, mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹, 14.6 k cal., 2.06×10^9 l, mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ and -17.2 e.u. respectively. A mechanism of the oxidation of 2, methyl 2,4-pentane diol by peroxydisulphate catalysed by silver(I) has been suggested.

Kinetic studies on oxidation of a variety of substances, both organic and inorganic by peroxydisulphate have been reviewed by House¹ and Wilmarth and Haim². Unless a catalyst is employed these reactions are slow at ordinary temperatures. The most thoroughly investigated catalyst is silver(I)³, although copper(II) has also been studied⁴. The present report deals with the results on the oxidation of 2, methyl 2,4-pentane diol by peroxydisulphate catalysed by silver(I).

EXPERIMENTAL

2, methyl 2,4-pentane diol (B.D.H. AnalaR), silver nitrate (B.D.H. AnalaR) and potassium peroxydisulphate (E. Merck) were used. All other chemicals were chemically pure. Standard solutions of the various reagents were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of reagents in double distilled water from pyrex vessel. Further, persulphate solution was always freshly prepared and its concentration checked by iodometry⁵.

The desired volumes of water and standard solutions, except for peroxydisulphate were placed in a glass-stoppered bottle. This bottle and another one containing peroxydisulphate were placed in a thermostat at temperature 48.5°, and allowed to reach thermal equilibrium. Then the appropriate volume of peroxydisulphate was transferred to the flask by means of a pipette. Aliquot portions of the solution were removed at known intervals of time and the concentration of peroxydisulphate left unreacted estimated by the method of Bartlett and Cotman.

The experiments were carried out in diffused room light since experiments showed that the rate of reaction in diffused room light is not significantly different from that in dark.

RESULTS

Stoichiometry : A 1 : 1 stoichiometry for $\Delta S_2O_8^{-2}/\Delta$ Diol was evaluated from 85% completed reactions by estimating $S_2O_8^{-2}$ and corresponding 2 : 4 dinitrophenyl hydrazones. The reaction may be represented by the following stoichiometric equation :

Acetone was identified by treating a drop of sample solution with a drop of alkaline solution of *o*-nitro benzaldehyde in a test tube and warmed in water bath, the cooled mixture was extracted with chloroform. A blue colour in chloroform layer indicated presence of acetone.

Since the rate laws are not affected by presence or absence of oxygen, no attempt was made to remove oxygen from the reaction system. The plot of $\log [S_2O_8^{-2}]$ versus time gave straight line indicating first order dependence of the rate on $[S_2O_8^{-2}]$.

The first order dependence on the concentration of peroxydisulphate was further verified by changing the initial concentration of peroxydisulphate (cf. Table 1). The fact that the pseudo first order rate constant is independent of the initial concentration of peroxydisulphate shows that the order with respect to peroxydisulphate is one, however, small decrease in rate constants with increase in concentration of oxidant may be ascribed to specific inhibitory effect of potassium ions.

TABLE 1

[2, Methyl 2,4-pentane diol] = $4.76 \times 10^{-2} M$				
[Ag ⁺] = $12.87 \times 10^{-4} M$				
Temp. 48.5°				
[S ₂ O ₈ ⁻²] × 10 ³ moles litre ⁻¹	0.052	1.91	2.86	4.76
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	4.27	4.10	3.72	3.20

The pseudo first order rate constant is independent of the concentration of 2, methyl 2,4-pentane diol, (cf. Table 2). This shows that the rate is independent of the initial concentration of 2, methyl 2,4-pentane diol.

TABLE 2

[S ₂ O ₈ ⁻²] = $1.90 \times 10^{-3} M$					
[Ag ⁺] = $12.87 \times 10^{-4} M$					
Temp. 48.5°					
[2, Methyl 2,4-pentane diol] × 10 ² mole litre ⁻¹	0.952	1.90	2.86	3.80	4.76
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	3.22	3.20	3.29	3.34	3.19

The pseudo first order constant is proportional to the first power of the concentration of silver(I) (cf. Table 3). This shows that the rate is directly proportional to the concentration of silver(I).

TABLE 3

[2, methyl 2,4-pentane diol] = $4.76 \times 10^{-2} M$
 [S₂O₈⁻²] = $4.76 \times 10^{-3} M$ Temp. 48°

[Ag ⁺] × 10 ⁴ mole litre ⁻¹	7.72	10.3	12.9	15.4	18.00	20.6
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	2.21	2.68	3.01	4.44	5.17	5.76
k ₁ /[Ag ⁺]	0.29	0.26	0.23	0.29	0.29	0.28

The effect of H⁺ ion concentration on the rate of oxidation was studied by adding sulphuric acid, at the same time adjusting the concentration of sulphate to a constant value by adding potassium sulphate. The results (cf. Table 4) show that small quantities of acid decrease rate constant appreciably, but further addition of acid (pH 2.5–3.6) does not produce any change in oxidation.

TABLE 4

[2, methyl, 2,4-pentane diol] = $4.76 \times 10^{-2} M$ Temp. 48.5°
 [S₂O₈⁻²] = $4.76 \times 10^{-3} M$, [SO₄⁻²] = $0.238 M$, [Ag⁺] = $12.87 \times 10^{-4} M$

[H ⁺] × 10 ² moles litre ⁻¹	0.00	4.76	9.52	14.28	19.04
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	2.99	1.51	1.28	1.51	1.65

The reaction was studied at different temperatures. The values of the pseudo-first order rate constants k_1 and of specific rate constant k ($k = k_1/[Ag^+]$) at different temperatures are summarised in Table 5.

TABLE 5

[2, methyl 2,4-pentane diol] = $4.76 \times 10^{-2} M$
 [S₂O₈⁻²] = $4.76 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Ag⁺] = $12.87 \times 10^{-4} M$

Temp. °C	31.0	40.0	48.8	54.0
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	0.840	1.32	2.99	4.35
k = k ₁ /[Ag ⁺] 1. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	0.065	0.103	0.233	0.338

DISCUSSION

The reaction between 2-methyl-2,4-pentane diol and peroxydisulphate in absence of silver(I) ions is extremely slow. The rate of (Ag⁺) ions catalysed reaction is proportional to the concentration of (Ag⁺) ions and peroxydisulphate but independent of the concentration of 2-methyl 2,4-pentane diol. Since the uncatalysed reaction between peroxydisulphate and 2-methyl-2,4-pentane diol is extremely slow, it therefore suggests that peroxydisulphate or sulphate radical ions do not react with 2-methyl-2,4-pentane diol. However, to explain the increased rate of disappearance of peroxydisulphate on addition of substrate, it is necessary to postulate that reactive silver species and 2-methyl-2,4-pentane diol react

to produce radical. The radical so produced from the substrate further induces peroxydisulphate decomposition. Gupta and Ghosh⁶ have proposed a mechanism involving an equilibrium which is followed by a termolecular rate determining step.

The breakdown of the peroxydisulphate into sulphate ion radicals appears to be unlikely since one would expect that the sulphate ion radicals would exchange electrons with sulphate ions at a rate comparable with their recombination to peroxydisulphate. However no exchange has been observed under the conditions of the kinetic experiments^{7,8,9,10}. Consequently any proposed mechanism of decomposition involving equilibrium between peroxydisulphate and sulphate ion radicals i.e. step (1) is probably incorrect.

Alternatively catalytic effect of silver ions may be explained by considering the following reactions :

The nature of the silver intermediate in the oxidations by peroxydisulphate is uncertain. Both Ag^{+2} and Ag^{+3} ions have been postulated as intermediates^{11,12,13}. The assumption that Ag^{+2} and SO_4^- are the chief reactive species is in agreement with the observations of Subbaraman and Santappa¹⁴, Higginson and Marshall that one electron transfer is more likely in oxidation reduction system between a transition metal ion and an ion derived from non transition element. Increasing μ by adding $\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{KNO}_3$ resulted in small decrease of the rate, no specific relationship was obtained by plotting $\sqrt{\mu}$ against $\log k$. This shows that salt effects seem to be unimportant, an observation similar to that of Subbaraman and Santappa, Gupta and Nigam¹⁵ in persulphate oxidations involving ions in rate determining steps. Confirmation of acetone as sole product further indicates the rupture of C-C bond nearest to the more alkylated carbon atom.

The fact that the rate of reaction is faster in solutions from which oxygen has been removed suggests a chain mechanism. In view of the above considerations we are led to suggest the following mechanism, which is consistent with the results.

By application of the Bodenstein principle i.e., neglecting the variation of $[\text{Ag}^{+2}]$, $[\text{CH}_3\text{CHOH}\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2]$, and $[\text{SO}_4^{-}]$ with time, one obtains

$$\frac{-d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{-2}]}{dt} = k[\text{Ag}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{-2}]$$

where $k = k_3 + k_6\{k_3k_4/k_6k_7\}^{\frac{1}{2}}$. This mechanism leads to correct rate laws and explains the dependence of rate constant on the first power of silver(I) ion concentration.

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